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EDITORIAL NOTE

It is with great pride and enthusiasm that we present the maiden edition of the *Gamji Journal of Arts and Humanities*, published by the Gamji Institute for Training and Research. This inaugural publication marks a significant milestone in our commitment to fostering academic excellence and contributing to the scholarly discourse in various fields of study.

The articles featured in this edition represent a diverse range of research topics, each offering valuable insights and advancing our understanding of critical issues. The depth and breadth of the studies reflect the dedication and scholarly rigor of the authors, and we are honored to showcase their work.

We extend our heartfelt gratitude to the authors for their invaluable contributions and to the peer reviewers for their diligent efforts in ensuring the quality and integrity of the research presented. We also express our appreciation to the editorial board and support staff whose dedication and hard work have made this publication possible.

As we embark on this scholarly journey, we invite readers to engage with the research presented in this journal, to reflect on the insights offered, and to contribute to the ongoing dialogue in their respective fields. We look forward to future editions and the continued growth of the *Gamji Journal of Arts and Humanities* as a platform for academic excellence and intellectual exchange.

Sincerely,

Prof. Aminu Ahmad
Chairman, Editorial Board
Gamji Journal of Arts and Humanities
Gamji Institute for Training and Research

ASSESSMENT OF PUBLIC POLICY IMPLEMENTATION OF THE PUBLIC PROCUREMENT ACT 2007 IN THE CODE OF CONDUCT BUREAU (CCB) ABUJA, NIGERIA

By

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ABSTRACT

The study is an assessment of the Public Policy Implementation of Public Procurement Act 2007 in the Code of Conduct Bureau (CCB) Abuja, Nigeria in compliance with the tenets enshrined in the Public Procurement Act 2007 during the procurement processes of works, goods and services. The 2007 Public Procurement Act serves as a compass for public sector procurement process in Nigeria with emphasis on the tenets of transparency, accountability, competitiveness and value for money. Engaging a qualitative research design, the research delves into the Code of Conduct Bureau (CCB) specifically to assess its procurement procedures, and see if it is in compliance with the stipulated Public Procurement Act, 2007. The documentary method of research design was employed. Useful documents and data were sorted from secondary sources such as Annual Reports and records of number of contracts awarded and executed. The major findings of the study revealed that there is significant impact of the implementation of the Public Procurement Act 2007 in the Code of Conduct (CCB) on the level of accountability in its procurement processes. The Public Procurement Act, 2007 does significantly contributed to the Code of Conduct Bureau (CCB) Abuja in ensuring transparency in the procurement of goods and services. Another major findings of the study showed that the Bureau adhered to the implementation tenets of the public procurement Act 2007 which led to achieving cost-effectiveness in the Bureau. The finding also revealed that there is a fostering competitiveness' in the procurement of goods and services in the Bureau. Based on its findings, the study recommended, among others, regular training programmes for procurement officers in the Bureau to enhance their service delivery of its personnel in compliance with the Procurement Act 2007. The study also recommended that the Bureau should evoke internal monitoring

mechanisms and compliance strategies to ensure strict adherence to the provisions of the Act and deviants should be severely apprehended and punished in accordance with the instant law establishing the Public Procurement Act, 2007.

Keywords: Public Policy, Policy implementation, Public Procurement Act, Code of Conduct Bureau.

1. INTRODUCTION

The major channel whereby government stimulates the economy is through expenditure. This spending goes beyond salaries and wages, but mainly through projects and acquisitions by government institutions. Purchase are made through government and state-owned enterprises for wide variety of goods, services and public works (from basic computer equipments to the construction of roads, bridges, dams and infrastructures) from the private sector of the economy. Public procurement is a major economic activity of governments that represents a significant percentage of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP), generating huge financial flows across the universe. An efficient and effective procurement system plays a strategic role for governments in avoiding mismanagement, misappropriation and waste of public funds (OECD, 2016).

In its quest to ensure sanity in public spending, the federal government of Nigeria and in realization that failures in the procurement process aid corruption in public space of governance, invited the World Bank to conduct the first of its kind nationwide assessment of public procurement law and practice. The result of that assessment conducted out in conjunction with a national task force, Country procurement Assessment Report (CPAR) 2000, formed the basis of the Public Procurement Bill later sent to the National Assembly, revised and enacted into law in 2007 as the Public Procurement Act, 2007 (Ekpenkhio, 2003).

The Public Procurement Act, 2007 was enacted in Nigeria to serve as the global best practice on sanitation of public procurement processes. The Act stipulates that all public procurements in Nigeria, as from the date of its commencement must follow due process, that is, it must be certified by a public procurement office established specifically to

analyze public procurements and issue a certificate of NO objection. This is because procurement is a major cost centre for any nation and is important in the provision of infrastructure (Ndeto, 2017).

Nonetheless, procurement has always been shrouded in secrecy and corruption. The challenge with procurement in Nigeria has always been that of transparency and authenticity. Public Procurement has become an issue of discuss for public attention and debate and has been subjected to reforms, restructuring, rules and regulations.

According to World Bank (1995), public procurement refers to the acquisition of goods, services and works by a procuring entity using public funds. Hui et al (2011) opined that due to the colossal amount of money involved in government procurement and the fact that such money comes from the public, there is a need for accountability and transparency.

In light of the above, both developed and underdeveloped countries have instituted procurement reforms through laws and regulations. Inadequate regulatory compliance is the main obstacle. This affects not only third-world countries but also countries in developed economies. Hui et al (2011), while analyzing procurement problems in Malaysia, instituted that procurement officers were blame for malpractice and non-compliance with procurement policies and procedures.

The Public Procurement Act, 2007 (PPA) is the law that seeks to regulate and control the process of acquisition of goods, works, or services by the Federal Government, its ministries, departments, parastatals, and agencies. Before the enactment of the Nigerian Public Procurement Act in 2007, there were no specific procedures laid down for the procurement of public goods and services in Nigeria. The implication of this was that every procurement entity in Nigeria, such as government institutions, was at liberty to decide and adopt any procurement method and strategy of their choice to determine and award contracts to contractors of their choice. These were the observed lapses largely responsible for the procurement of public goods and services such as procurement of substandard products, corruption, project abandonment, project failure, high cost of procurement, flagrant abuse of procedures for the award of public contract, inflation of

contract costs, lack of transparency, competence-based competition, and merit as the fundamental criteria for the award of public contracts.

The inconsistencies perceived led to the enactment of the Budget Monitoring and Price Intelligence Unit (BMPIU) in the Presidency. This unit, popularly called the “Due Process” unit, was charged with the responsibility of reducing, to the barest minimum, the observed massive flagrant abuse of the procedure for procurement of public goods and services in Nigeria. The unit later metamorphosed or snow blow into the National Council on Public Procurement and the Bureau of Public Procurement by the passage of the Public Procurement Act, 2007.

The first concrete action was taken to addressing this needed Act was addressed by the executive submission of executive bill to the National Assembly which led to the enactment in 2000 of the Independent Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Commission (ICPC) Act. Realizing the failures in the procurement process contributed to the corruption in governance and in order to identify the loopholes in the process, the first step was to introduce acceptable international standard practices in the regulation of public procurement in Nigeria.

The CPAR was a detailed diagnosis of the Nigerian procurement system and included both findings and recommendations (Ekpenkhio, 2003). Following the country’s Procurement Assessment Report and prior to the preparation of the bill for procurement reforms, the Federal Government moved to implement the recommendations of CPAR to the extent possible prior to legislative reforms. In June 2003, the government established the Budget Monitoring and Price Intelligence Unit (BMPIU), which is an operationally independent body under the Director of a Senior Special Assistant to the President. Although thinly staffed, its personnel comprised experts with a bias for project management, construction, and procurement. The unit was the clearinghouse for all Federal Government contracts and procurements of goods and services, and functions, until the commencement of implementation of the Public Procurement Act, 2007 (Ekpenkhio, 2003). The Bureau for Monitoring, Price Intelligence Unit (BMPIU) operated under clear goals, objectives, and strategies. Its goal was to put in place and ensure full compliance with laid-down guidelines and procedures (produced by it) for the

procurement of capital and minor capital projects as well as associated goods and services. Its objectives are to:

1. Harmonize existing government policies/practices on public procurement and update same.
2. Determine whether or not Due Process has been observed in the procurement of goods and services.
3. Promote honesty, accountability and transparency into the procurement process.
4. Establish and update pricing standards and benchmarks for all supplies to government.
5. Monitor the implementation of projects during execution with a view to providing information on performance, output and compliance with specifications and targets.
6. Ensure that only projects which has been budgeted for are accepted for execution.

The strategies of the BMPIU revolved primarily around: regulatory, certification, monitoring, training and advisory functions. After the enactment of the Public Procurement Act to take over the functions of BMPIU and implement the provisions of the Act, the Bureau also inherited the staff and physical structure of the BMPIU.

In spite of the operation of the Act, the achievement of accountability in public procurement by public sectors is still a mirage. Value for money was hardly achieved. Public procurement seems not to have been carried out in the most transparent manner. Cost-effectiveness in the purchase of goods and services by public sectors were hardly achieved, competition of bidders was barely achieved in the public procurement processes of goods and services. The purpose of this study thus is to make available answers on how to reduce wastages in public sector procurements through adherence to the Public Procurement Act, 2007 and its tenets, in order to achieve accountability, value for money, transparency and cost-effectiveness. The main objective of the study is to assess the public policy implementation of public procurement Act 2007 in the Code of Conduct Bureau (CCB) Abuja, Nigeria on the strict adherence to the fundamental tenets for

procurements in the procurement processes of goods, works and services in line with Part (IV) Section 16 of the Procurement Act 2007.

2. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

In line with the study statement above, the research provides the following questions:

1. To what extent has the policy implementation of Public Procurement Act, 2007 assisted the Code of Conduct Bureau (CCB) in ensuring accountability in the procuring process of goods and service?
2. How did the Public Policy implementation of Public Procurement Act, 2007 contributed to Code of Conduct Bureau (CCB), achieving the tenets of value for money in the procurement processes?
3. In which ways has the Public Procurement Act, 2007 aided the Code of Conduct Bureau (CCB), achieve cost-effectiveness in the procurement of goods and services?

3. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

1. Examine the extent public policy implementation of the Public Procurement Act 2007 assisted the Code of Conduct Bureau (CCB) in ensuring accountability in the procurement process of goods and services.
2. Ascertain the contributions of the Public Procurement Act, 2007 towards the achievement of value for money in procurement processes undertaken by the Code of Conduct Bureau (CCB)
3. Assess how the public policy implementation of the Public Procurement Act, 2007 has aided the Code of Conduct Bureau (CCB) in achieving cost-effectiveness in the procurement of goods and services

4. CONCEPTUALIZATION

4.1 Concept of Public Policy

The concept of policy in most recent times today is a popular discourse saturated with the criticism or advocacy of many policies. It is often heard of economic policy, educational policy, defense policy, policy on corruption, policy on health services and policies in most

areas of government and private transactions. Moving forward, we also hear policy statements, enactment of policies and declaration of policy intentions and the commitments of billions of hard and Nigerian Naira for the implementation of some basic policies. We live in an era which is affected and influenced by policies made by governments and societies, communities, churches, social organisations, educational businesses, labour groups. The outcomes of policies are also all round us. The provision of social services, the availability, the cost of fuel and gas or non-availability of imported goods and services, the scope of our economic activities, the security of our jobs and how much tax we pay or rate to pay the availability of agricultural loans and employment opportunities are all determined by or are the results of policies (Ikelegbe, 1994)

It is in light of this that Public Policy is defined as a governmental decision or non-decision designed to deal with various social problems such as kidnapping, armed robbery, electoral violence, education, agricultural, economy and oil bunkering. The two cardinal significant features of this definition are governmental decision or non-decision and social problems. Government takes decisions aimed at resolving or solving a particular problem or refuses to take a decision. Public Policy is related to the structure of government. For example, each level of the three tiers of government in Nigeria has the power to make public policies on issues within its constitutional domain or jurisdictions. (Ujo, 2011)

Anderson (1997) in Katuka (2013) sees Public Policy as behavior of some actors or set of actors such as officials, a government agencies or legislatures, in an area of activity such as public transportation, health, corruption, consumer protection, procurement activities etc.

4.2 PUBLIC POLICY IMPLEMENTATION

Casual observers may think that policy process is complete once a law is passed or an executive order is issued. However, the policy, once authorized, must be implemented. Implementation is the “***set of activities directed towards putting a programme into effect***” (Jones, 1984). Implementation is a complex process and can take months, or even years, to fully complete. Kraft and Furlong (2018) consider three activities crucial to successful implementation: Organisation, interpretation and application.

Organisation refers to the administration of the programme, particularly the resources allocated, and the personnel assigned. Interpretation addresses how the policy is understood by those responsible for administering the policy. Lastly, application is how the policy objectives are carried out or executed.

The executive - president, governors and chairmen of local governments are generally responsible for executing policies by way of bureaucratic agencies. Example of such agencies includes the Department of Health and Human Services at the federal level, the Department of Transportation at the state level, and the Parks and Recreation Department at the local level. Executives are also responsible for selecting agency heads to oversee policy execution. The President generally appoints officials who agree with him on programme objectives (commonly referred to as “yes-men”) and are experts in the field; they may also receive their appointment as patronage for supporting the executive in their bid for elected office. Abubakar Malammai, whom President Muhammadu Buhari appointed as Attorney General, was a proponent of uncontested executive power and is considered a yes-man by many.

Though the executive is responsible for policy execution, agencies rely on funding to administer programmes. The executive and legislative branch each put forth their budget priorities and negotiate to reach a final agreement before a budget is passed. The budget will allocate funds through appropriations. Agencies, thus, are constrained by both the legislature and executive, particularly during periods of divided government. Thus, it is incumbent on agency heads to maintain a strong, positive relationship with both the executive and legislative arm. The appropriation of a policy does not guarantee its success. The policy relies on personnel, funding, and buy-in by bureaucrats to implement the legislation as directed. Furthermore, policies may be overridden when a new executive is elected and the composition of the legislature changes - when, for example, party control in the National Assembly shifts - which could affect appropriations. Overrides can also occur if bureaucrats change their opinion on the policy, either due to personnel turnover or changes in resource allocation.

Policy implementation is an ongoing endeavour that will continue until the policy is terminated. Policy administrators, particularly the managers, must continuously monitor the policy and protect it from those who would like to see it fail. Bardach (1977) contended

that policy implementation can be looked at as one views a machine. A machine, much like public policy, is complex and has many moving parts that must work together to produce the desired output.

4.3 CODE OF CONDUCT BUREAU (CCB)

In 1986, the Political Bureau in its reports which the government accepted, observed that corruption and indiscipline were the bane of our political development. It recommended the strengthening of existing machineries for monitoring the acts and behaviours of public officers in the area of procurement, to ensure that they conform to the highest standards of public morality and accountability. Following this recommendation, a Code of Conduct Bureau (CCB) and Tribunal were established as the agencies to enforce the Code of Conduct for Public Officers provided for in the 1979 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. The provision has maintained a permanence of some sort, in the Fifth Schedule of the Constitutions that followed thereafter, notably the 1999 Constitution (as Amended).

The Code of Conduct Bureau (CCB) and Tribunal are two autonomous institutions that operate independently with clearly defined complementary roles. While the Bureau administers assets declarations and investigates complaints of breaches of the Code, the Tribunal adjudicates on the cases sent to it by the Bureau. Such cases are prosecuted by the office of the Attorney General of the Federation through its officers posted to the Bureau.

The aims and objectives of the Bureau

The aims and objectives of the Bureau is to establish and maintain a high standard of morality in the conduct of government business and to ensure that the actions and behaviours of public officers conform to the highest standards of public morality and accountability.

Functions of the Bureau

The functions of the Bureau shall be to:

1. Receive assets declaration by public officers in accordance with the provision of this Act

2. Examine the assets declarations and ensure that they comply with the requirements of this Act and of any law for the time being in force.
3. Take and retain custody of such assets declarations.
4. Receive complaints about noncompliance with or breach of this Act and where the Bureau considers it necessary to do so, refer such complaints to the Code of Conduct Tribunal established by Section 20 of this Act in accordance with the provisions of Section 20 to 25 of the Act.

The need for a code of conduct for public officers

The need for Code of Conduct for Public Officers in the young democratic state that Nigeria finds itself now cannot be over-emphasized. This is particularly so when viewed against the backdrop of large scale fraud and corruption which has become prevalent in the civil/public service. The inimical effects of the twin evil on the economic and social development of the country cannot be glossed over. Nigerians have suffered physical deprivation, arid poverty directly as a result of corruption in the areas of contracts which necessitated the promulgation of Public Procurement Act 2007. As for our external corporate image, it was scarred beyond recognition, with Nigeria being rated as a highly corrupt country and capital city of corruption in Africa. The time has come for Nigerians to rid themselves of this monster and cankerworm and to conscientize themselves towards acceptable behaviours. It was envisaged that a set of ethics and rules of behavior for public officers will go a long way in enhancing this resolve.

The Code of Conduct is to assist public servants to become accountable and to adopt transparent practices in their work. By painstaking studying these codes and endeavouring to imbibe them as part of their job, public officers were to save themselves the unpleasant consequence of having to face the Code of Conduct Bureau and the Anti-corruption law of 2000.

4.4 CONCEPT OF PUBLIC PROCUREMENT

In the wisdom of the World Bank (2015), public procurement is the process by which governments and other public funded entities acquire goods, works and services needed

to implement public projects. It accounts for at least 15% of the world's Gross Domestic Product (GDP), and even more underdeveloped countries of Africa.

The United Nations Development Programme (UNDP, 2007) sees public procurement as an overall process of acquiring goods, civil works, and services that includes all functions from the identification of needs, selection and solicitation of sources, preparation and award of contracts, and all phases of contract administration through the end of a service contract or the useful life of an asset.

Tukamuhabwa (2012) opined that Public Procurement is the process of assigning an external entity to obtain works, goods or services to be funded from the public treasury. From a general perspective, public procurement involves the procurement of goods and services by a third party on behalf of the government. Here, the government is referred to as a public entity, which could be various municipalities, ministries, provinces, agencies, or any other governmental organisation (Othman, Zakaria, Nordin, Shahidan, & Jusoff, 2010) According to Aregbesola (2016), "Procurement is one of the ways government interfaces with the people and enlivens its domestic economy". It is imperative that the resources of the government are managed judiciously and the procurement process be seen as transparent and equitable. Governments, as stewards of public funds, must be accountable and be seen to have gotten the best deal in procurement for the people with public funds.

Onuba (2016) stated that the Bureau of Public Procurement (BPP) had saved Nigeria a total of N658.88bn (about \$1.833bn) from inflated contracts submitted by contractors of the Ministries, Departments, and Agencies (MDAs) of the Federal Government. The Bureau of Public Procurement was created in 2007 through Public Procurement Act No. 14 to supervise public procurement practices and recommend the best public procurement methods for different goods and services procured by the governments' MDAs (Policy formulation, monitoring and evaluation). Most of the disagreements between clients and contractors arise because of the wrong choice of procurement methods and corruption. Ojo (1999) observed that in the Nigerian construction industry, the client and consultants do not have a specific procedure for choosing their procurement method to implement their projects but base it on familiarity with a particular method.

Public Procurement Act 2007

Jibrin et al (2014) said Reforms of Public Procurement was necessitated in Nigeria by transparency and accountability related issues due to rampant public procurement fraudulent practices in addition to conflict of interests. This has remained the sole reason for reforming public procurement processes in most of the countries that passed through the public procurement transformation process. The Federal Government of Nigeria instituted a robust Public Procurement System (PRS) for the execution of all government projects, works and services. It did this through the enactment of Public Procurement Act (PPA) 2007 as amended in 2018 (Kanu, Benedict & Akuwudike, 2020). The Public Procurement Act 2007 (PPA 2007) was enacted by the administration of Late President Umar Musa Yar'adua to instill discipline in the public procurement practice in Nigeria. In Nigeria, the Public Procurement Act is thus, the primary legislation which establishes the National Council on Procurement and Bureau of Public Procurement (BPP) as the regulators responsible for due process in Nigeria's procurement activities. The Public Procurement Act serves as a guide for the implementation of any public procurement that derive at least 35 percent funds appropriated or proposed to be appropriated from the consolidated Revenue Funds (Udoma & Osagie, 2012, Enofe, Okuonghae & Onobun, 2015).

Like most developing countries, the World Bank was the driving force behind public procurement reform in Nigeria (Williams-Elegbe, 2016). In Africa and Nigeria in particular, governance reform is expected to introduce acceptable benchmarks for legitimacy in public affairs while promoting economic choices among people and institutions. Part of the major benefits of governance reform is that it entrenches transparency, accountability, openness, and appropriate value for money in all matters that concern public procurement (Adewole, 2014; Ekwewuo, 2016). The Public procurement bill was sent to the National Assembly in 2003, and by June 4, 2007, the Public Procurement Act was passed in Nigeria, which became a watershed in Nigeria's attempt at key governance reform. The Public Procurement Act, 2007 is designed primarily after the United Nations Commission on International Trade Law's (UNCITRAL) Model Law on Public Procurement (Eze, 2015, Ezeh, 2013; Familoye et al, 2015, Udeh, 2015). The report on Nigeria's procurement assessment identified some

weaknesses in the then existing procurement system, which includes lack of appropriate legislation, shortage of basic skills, and inappropriate organization of the procurement process (World Bank, 2000).

Achievement of the Bureau of Public Procurement

In the view of Ezech (2013), these are the specific achievements of the Bureau of Public Procurement in Nigeria:

1. Publication and Circulation of the Public Procurement Act, 2007 (PPA).
2. Issuance of Procurement Regulations.
3. Issuance of Procurement Procedures Manuals.
4. Issuance of Standard Bidding Document for Works, Goods, and Consultancy Services.
5. Translation of Public Procurement Act 2007 into the major Nigerian languages of Igbo, Yoruba and Hausa.
6. Functional Procurement Data Centre.
7. Functional Bureau of Public Procurement website.
8. Publishing of a Quarterly Procurement Journal since 2008.
9. Publishing the procurement plans of the MDAs since 2009.
10. Publishing of Procurement Records of MDAs since 2009.
11. Uploading of Federal Executive Council (FEC) approved contracts to the Bureau of Public Procurement website.
12. Publishing details of all contracts awarded in print media and on the Bureau's website.

According to Adewole (2014), the on-going development and capable contractors are invited to tender for government projects. Part III (section 15: Scope of Application) of Public Procurement Law 2007 deals with the scope of applications. This aspect of the law respects the Federal nature of Nigeria as a nation-state, where states are expected to enact

their own laws as they deem fit; the public procurement Act presumptively should cover only Federal Public Procurements.

Challenges of the Public Procurement Act 2007 in the Code of Conduct Bureau (CCB)

According to Yusuf (2023), there are several challenges in public procurement implementation in Nigeria which are prevalent in the Code of Conduct Bureau (CCB).

Some of the challenges include:

1. **Lack of transparency:** There is often a lack of transparency in the procurement process, which makes it cumbersome to hold government officials accountable for their actions. This lack of transparency can also lead to favouritism and bias in the award of contracts.
2. **Corruption:** Corruption is a major challenge in public procurement in Nigeria. It often leads to inflated contract prices, poor quality of goods and services, and the awarding of contracts to unqualified or politically connected individuals or companies.
3. **Inadequate legal framework:** The legal framework for public procurement in Nigeria is often inadequate, which can lead to loopholes and inconsistencies in the procurement process. This can make it cumbersome to enforce regulations and ensure fair competition.
4. **Weak institution capacity:** Many government agencies like the Bureau responsible for public procurement lack the capacity and expertise to effectively implement procurement processes. This can result in delays, inefficiencies, and mismanagement of resources.
5. **Political interference:** Political interference in public procurement is a common challenge in Nigeria. Politicians often influence the procurement process to benefit themselves or their associates, leading to unfair competition and the award of contracts based on political considerations rather than merit.
6. **Weak monitoring and Evaluation:** The monitoring and evaluation of procurement processes are often weak in Nigeria. This makes it cumbersome to assess the

effectiveness and efficiency of procurement activities and identify areas for improvement.

7. **Limited access to information:** There is often limited access to information about procurement processes, making it cumbersome for the public and civil society organisations to monitor and scrutinize government spendings. This lack of transparency can further exacerbate corruption and mismanagement.

Addressing these challenges requires a comprehensive approach that includes strengthening the legal framework, improving transparency and accountability, enhancing institutional capacity, prompting citizen engagement, and implementing effective monitoring and evaluation mechanisms.

In addition, he further stated that the procurement process in Nigeria is a set of procedures and guidelines that govern the acquisition of goods, works and services by government agencies and parastatals. The process is designed to ensure transparency, accountability, and value for money in public procurement.

Steps involved in the Procurement Process

Here are the steps involved in the procurement process in Nigeria:

1. **Planning:** This involves identifying the need for goods, works, or services and developing a procurement plan that outlines the requirements, specifications, and budget.
2. **Advertising:** This involves publishing a tender notice in national newspapers and on the procurement agency's website, inviting bids from interested parties.
3. **Bid Evaluation:** This involves evaluating the bids received based on the criteria outlined in the tender documents and selecting the most suitable bidder.
4. **Contract Award:** This involve awarding the contract to the successful bidder and signing a contract agreement that outlines the terms and conditions of the procurement.
5. **Contract Management:** This involves monitoring the performance of the contractor, ensuring compliance with the contract terms, and making payments as due.

6. **Contract Closeout:** This involves closing out the contract after completion and conducting final evaluation of the contractor's performance. It is significant to note that a number of laws, rules and regulations, including the Public Procurement Act of 2007, the Nigeria Content Development and Monitoring Board Act, and the Bureau of Public Procurement regulations control the procurement process in Nigeria

5. EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Ogolo (2010) evaluated the implementation of Public Procurement process in selected Federal Government establishments. Public Procurement is part of the new economic reforms meaning to ensure transparency and accountability in the use of public resources in Nigeria. Descriptive statistics was used to analyse the responses stated in the liker scale. The study employed chi-square to test the parameters in the hypotheses. It is found that procurement process is characterized with accountability, transparency, value for money and a cleansing mechanism in the Nigeria public sector of which 79% of the respondents strongly agreed. It is also found that there is total relegation of rules and lack of capacity in the system especially in adhering to advertising, bidding, tendering, screening, competitiveness and defense of government contract procurements. It is recommended that public procurement process should be continued and broadened. It was also recommended that the system be improved to full capacity by incorporating more qualified and reputable persons in the technical committee of the procurement processes.

Fayomi, Ikeoluwapo Omolara (2013) examined Public Procurement and due process policy in Nigeria: Thrust, prospects and challenges. The study review at independence in 1960, Nigeria had very high hopes and expectations for rapid and superlative socio-economic growth and development. Regrettably enough, Nigeria today can be described as a country of irony as the socio-economic performance over the years remained superficial and unimpressive. This inclement experience was largely attributed to high level of corruption or mismanagement of public resources closely linked up with the public sector procurement systems that has brought untold hardship on the economy and the citizens. To reverse this irony of poverty in the midst of plenty, the government introduced the universal "Best Practices", the Procurement process mechanism in the

country's public procurement system in 2001. However, a lot of questions, misconceptions and criticisms have trailed its implementation which has made it increasingly cumbersome to secure maximum affection from the majority of the Nigerian populace. Findings revealed that the policy has been adjudged to have performed below public expectations. He thus recommended that governments should do all things possible through sincere political will, not only to sustain it but to re-invigorate it by putting "biting razor teeth and a "hot iron knots" to cracks or leakages through which the policy is being abused or mocked.

Ayangade, Wahab, and Alake (2009) investigated the level of impression on procurement process by parties involved in the award of public contracts, the performance of public procurement process and factors that may affect its functions. The survey was carried out by administering structured questionnaire and interviews on the practitioners in the construction industry that were in the private and public sectors. The data collected were analysed with the use of both descriptive and inferential statistics. The study revealed that procurement process has become a new initiative being widely embraced by parties in public contract and has aided in saving public fund by corrupt practices. The study also showed that the absence of legal and other institutional frameworks were among the factors that affect the performance of public procurement process in the country.

Atagboro (2015) examined whether procurement process mechanisms serve as an antidote for fraudulent practices in the Nigerian public sector. Using 875 subjects in the public sector, the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation statistical tool was employed in order to establish whether procurement process mechanism is an antidote for fraudulent practices and also to see if the procurement ensures transparency and is an antidote for fraudulent practices. Another interesting finding from extant literature was that weak internal control system encourages fraudulent practices in the public sector. Therefore, the need to re-embark upon moral, religious, ethnic and social re-orientation in the public sector on the path of economic progress and development and not for political merits is eminent as well as rigorous campaigns to awaken the conscious and re-orient public servants and the general society on the need to refrain from fraud or abetting it. The internal control system operating in the public sector needs to be strengthened. Also, there is need for institutionalizing, internalizing and building ownership for the multitude

of reforms within the public sector so as to ensure that it sustains the changes in the anti-corruption campaign in Nigeria.

Over the years, various methods have been used for procuring projects. Some of the procurement methods were amended and updated to form standards for clients should be based on the experience and advice of relevant professionals. Professional often perform dual roles on the same project and this should not be so. Hence, in view of the unique characteristics of the construction industry, there is a great need for the improvement of current procurement systems so as to assist in improving the products of the industry and the image of the professionals.

6. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The theoretical insight into this study is situated with Systems Theory propounded by David Easton, a distinguished political scientist, who left an indelible mark on the discipline through his substantial contributions to the evolution of political system theory. His seminal work, encapsulated in the book “A System Analysis of Political Life” (1965), serves as a cornerstone for comprehending the intricacies of political systems. Easton’s scholarly endeavors were dedicated to unraveling the complexities inherent in these systems, portraying them as dynamic entities.

Influentially, in his discourse, Easton advocated a holistic approach, urging scholars to scrutinize political system in their entirety rather than fixating on isolated components. His central thesis underscored the interconnectivity of political phenomena, contending that a comprehensive understanding necessitates a meticulous examination of the intricate relationships and interactions among the various elements constituting the system.

The crux of Easton’s perspective lies in the conviction that dissecting political system in isolation obscures the broader tapestry of their functioning. He posited that only through a systemic analysis could one decipher the nuanced interplay between the myriad components, shedding light on the underlying mechanisms steering the course of political life. Easton’s legacy endures as a beacon guiding scholars to approach the study of political systems with a holistic lens, appreciating the intricate web of connections that defines their nature.

7. THE SYSTEM THEORY APPLICABILITY TO THIS STUDY

David Easton's System Theory, which was formulated during the 1950s and 1960s, stands as a foundational theoretical construct for understanding intricate political systems. This paradigm delves into the intricate web of interrelated components and processes inherent in political systems, elucidating their collaborative efforts to sustain stability and adapt to evolving circumstance. When applied to evaluate the implementation of the Public Procurement Act policy in the Code of Conduct Bureau (CCB), Systems Theory furnishes an exhaustive framework. This framework facilitates a nuanced exploration of the multifaceted interactions and dynamics inherent in the procurement process. By embracing System Theory, analysts gain a holistic lens that considers the interconnectedness of diverse components, allowing for a thorough examination of their collective impact on the overall efficacy of policy implementation within the Code of Conduct Bureau (CCB).

8. METHODOLOGY

This study relied on secondary sources of data, which in turn was analyzed using descriptive qualitative approach. The specific documents used were: copies of mapping and scoping surveys of anti-corruption and governance measures in public financial management, public Procurement Laws, Procurement Guidelines/Procedure Manual, Due Process Law/Manual, Standard bidding Documents, and other implementing documents. Also documents like the Public/Civil Service Rule, Anti-corruption Law. Freedom of Information Law was utilized. Other secondary data used for the analysis of this study were accessed from official websites, textbooks, annual reports, journals, magazines, conferences, internet facilities and seminar papers, records on contract awards. Newspapers and other qualitative publications related to the problem of the study were all systematically analyzed.

9. FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

The legal, regulation and practice of public procurement in most government institutions or agencies in Nigeria has not witnessed substantial or appreciable improvements judging from best practices as indicated in Treaties advanced by the United Nations Convention Against Corruption (UNCAC), the African Union Convention on Preventing

and Combating Corruption (AUCPCC), and ECOWAS Protocol on the Fight Against Corruption. The treaties require that state parties adopt measures aimed at promoting best practices. However, the findings reveal that even in most government institutions or agencies where public procurement laws have been practiced, progress is relatively slow. Most institutions or agencies started implementation in any determinable form except establishment of State Council of Public Procurement (SCPP). The study found that:

1. The Code of Conduct Bureau (CCB) has commenced the implementation of Public Procurement Act since its domestication in Nigeria and there has been appreciable improvement in the fight against corruption in terms of contract awards.
2. There is need to train all the procurement officers to become more efficient and effective in the performance of their responsibility as procurement officers.
3. Lack of adequate funding is one of the main findings noticed during the study in which the Code of Conduct Bureau procurement unit is confronting in the execution of the award of contracts.
4. The Bureau unit of the procurement is dire need of office accommodation to enable it perform its duties effectively and efficiently.
5. There is due interference by the management in the award of contract in the Code of Conduct Bureau (CCB) thereby making it cumbersome for the unit to be independent of their duty.
6. There is absence of advance establishment of selection and award criteria in the deployment and use of regulations and standard documents in all procurement activities in the Code of Conduct Bureau (CCB).

10. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the study findings, the following recommendations are put forward to aid strengthen the practice of public procurement in the Code of Conduct Bureau (CCB) in line with global best practices:

1. Award and reward should be giving to transparent and prudent personnel staff of the procurement unit to serve as an appreciation and corrupt personnel be severely punished to serve as deterrence to others intending to do personnel.

2. The study also recommends that the personnel of the procurement unit in the Code of Conduct Bureau (CCB) should be given adequate training and retraining on the area of procurement of contract by engaging experts to give them training. That will give the motivation to put in their best in their responsibilities.
3. Government should be deliberate in funding the procurement unit in order to enable the award of contract unhindered by paying for the projects executed in due time.
4. It is also recommended that the Code of Conduct Bureau in collaboration with the Bureau of Public Procurement office should provide adequate office accommodation for the procurement unit of the Code of Conduct Bureau (CCB) to carry out their respective responsibility without any hinge.
5. There should be very strong rules preventing the management of the Code of Conduct Bureau (CCB) from due interference with the award of contract by the procurement unit and failure to obey such rules, a stiffer sanction be given to the management to serve as a deterrence to others within and outside the Bureau.
6. In addition to a law through which government institutions or agencies may ensure advance establishment of selection and award criteria is the deployment and use of regulations and standard documents in all procurement activities. These instruments in addition to being a guide to establishing these criteria can also provide benchmarks for measurement of compliance.

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